

GRANT AGREEMENT NUMBER

101035819

This project has received funding from the European Union's
Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme

**ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH
AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A
GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE**

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
3	D3.3	D19	Map of DI/AI initiatives, tools and methods in ENLIGHT	UU

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	D 3.1, D 5.1

Description (short)
The report brings together initiatives, tools and methods in the DI/AI Digital Ecosystem of the ENLIGHT Alliance in order to identify possibilities related to the ENLIGHT R&I Agenda.

Document Version Control		
Version 0.2	Margaretha Andersson, Sebastien Peyrard	UU, UBx
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7785779	

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Executive Summary

Access to world-class digital research infrastructure is a cornerstone of a competitive ENLIGHT RISE R&I agenda. Within the ENLIGHT Alliance there is a common ambition to open up for researchers and students to join forces with society, e.g. business sector, non-governmental organizations and decisionmaking bodies, to make impact on societal challenges. There is also a strong wish to accelerate DI/AI knowledge transmission and reinforce the societal return on investment.

This report gives an overview describing commitment on policy level and readiness in the digital ecosystems as well as platforms, centres of competence and support functions of importance to fulfil the ENLIGHT R&I agenda. In the Appendix, local organizational functions, tools/services and examples demonstrating best practise in the digital area are presented. Access to updated examples demonstrating an ability to build a track record in areas of relevance for the DI/AI agenda are also available via the set of links.

The awareness and commitment to digital strategies among the ENLIGHT universities are obvious. The Alliance is also well connected and have access to first class infrastructure suitable for undertakings related to the Flagship Areas decided by ENLIGHT. A critical mass of expert users and a surrounding society/business sector making investments in digital means and methods are also identified. Entrepreneurial aspects are in general well recognized and many of the local business ecosystems are hosting a vibrant start-up scene. The flagship area of "Health and Well-being" is attracting interest from all partner universities, followed by the area of "Digital Revolution and Impact of Digitalization".

The acceleration aspect, however, substantially calls for coordination and alignment. In this area are the main challenges identified! Countries, regions and e.g. the organization of research and innovation differs within Europe. Differences may be due to legislation in areas as tax, privacy or language issues, or how governance is organized. Some countries have a strong intermediary level (regions, Bundesländer etc.) while others put responsibilities locally on universities (Sweden) or on the top national level where there is a close relationship with universities (Estonia).

Abbreviations

ENLIGHT partner	Short Name	Country
University of Bordeaux	UBx	FR
Ghent University	UGENT	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
University of Galway	GAL	IE
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE
University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE

AI – Artificial Intelligence

DIH – Digital Innovation Hub

EDIH – European Digital Innovation Hub

EEA – European Education Area

EOSC – European Open Science Cloud

ERA – European Research Area

DI – Digital Innovation

DRI – Digital Research Infrastructure

HPC – High Performance Computing

OS – Open Science

RI – Research Infrastructure

SSH - Social Sciences and Humanities

STEM – Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Introduction and Context

ENLIGHT is a so called European University formed by nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (Belgium, Estonia, France, Germany, Ireland, Netherlands, Slovakia, Spain & Sweden). ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the Horizon 2020 Science With and For Society (SWAFS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance.

Although the EU is a global leader in research and innovation, it continues to lag behind in translating R&I results into the economy. Retaining talent is a key and the new European Research Area (ERA) plans to improve researchers' employability and at the same time boost exchange and inter-sectoral mobility schemes involving industry. Since "connecting" and "sharing" are core values for ERA, EEA and the ENLIGHT-platform, access to digital resources for education, research and innovation are of crucial importance.

The ENLIGHT alliance gathers a strong knowledge community composed of highly competitive, entrepreneurial universities, increasingly networked with businesses and society. The long term objective is to create an ENLIGHT digital DI/AI ecosystem where academia and society may collaborate via digital infrastructural resources in order to address societal challenges.

The Context of ENLIGHT Alliance

ENLIGHT strives to transform the way in which we address global societal challenges by developing new models and methodologies for education and research adapted to the complex sustainability issues that cities and communities face today, originally focusing on five flagship areas

- Health and Well-being
- Digital Revolution and the Impact of Digitalization
- Climate Change
- Energy Transition and Circular Economy
- Equity

Characteristics of the Fields of Digital Innovation and Artificial Intelligence (DI/AI)

Huge resources are allocated into the areas of Digital Innovation and Artificial Intelligence. Funding is poured in from the EC in programs as e.g. Digital Europe, European Digital Innovation Hubs and additional national funding is added in coordination with decisions on European level. In addition, universities, private enterprises (SME:s as well as Google/Microsoft or Bytedance(China)), national funding agencies and local societal stakeholders (e.g. municipalities or healthcare providers) are also setting out for the digital

future. The field of DI/AI is vibrant and developing extremely fast. New initiatives emerge, old ones are replaced or undergo changes to meet developing societal expectations. Highly capitalized private initiatives are rapidly reaching market – and they may go for profit or political influence rather than societal transparency and data privacy. These trends are coming with risks!

According to the Roadmap presented in D 3.1 (figure below) the ENLIGHT-RISE project is now leaving the initial phase of Raising Awareness, Mapping, and Observing. In upcoming work within ENLIGHT-RISE WP 3, e.g. case studies, dialogue with DI/AI Network and an DI/AI Index, the project will dive deeper into practical experiences. Focus will be less on mapping tools and methods – and more on “HOW” we can use them to make impact together.

Exploring synergies in the digital landscape

In recent years, Europe has also invested large resources in research infrastructure. State-of-the-art experimental facilities reinforce Europe’s research and innovation system by providing researchers from academia and industry with instruments and other facilities. These platforms generate extensive collections of data sets of various sizes and types which require management, computing resources and storage. Major investments have been made in digital infrastructure like high-performance computers and connectivity networks (e-infrastructures), to process and disseminate data generated by research.

The landscape of research infrastructure as well as digital resources are characterized by coordination and scalability in order to create synergies and cost efficient funding. Large scale platforms are in general created and operated on “common ground” on the basis of funding from EU and the member states. Mid-size platforms may be national or regional while smaller resources are operated and funded locally. EU has identified Digital Europe as a key effort to maintain and develop at competitive knowledge and business area. Digital assets are also important in order to realize a Green Future. The distribution of small and large resources as well as locally decided funding in parallel with strategic partnerships are common – but difficult to quantify. As stated in D 3.1 the ENLIGHT Alliance have relationships related to almost all major

ESFRI initiatives as well as EOSC and Gaia-X. Where these relationships exist there are also excellent users already assessed by the scientific community.

This document represents the D 3.3 deliverable described as follows in the application:

“Existing initiatives, tools and methods to describe, analyse and reinforce the DI/AI policies, among ENLIGHT partners will be mapped. Mapping will include social, legal and ethical tools and processes. Tools, methodologies and best practices will be described at different levels, such as:

- 1) The use of DI/AI by ENLIGHT universities,*
- 2) Acceleration of DI/AI transmission,*
- 3) Research and innovation co-development of DI/AI between STEM and SSH.”*

Before going into details related to 1-3 above, an assessment of DI/AI Readiness and Maturity was performed. The exercise is intended to establish a framework of understanding related to local conditions.

DI/AI Maturity and Readiness within ENLIGHT Alliance

In order to analyse the degree of impact in the area of DI/AI related to ENLIGHT Digital Ecosystems, data was collected from different sources in order to visualize DI/AI maturity and readiness. Data indicate a degree of sustainability and diversity of the digital ecosystem associated with an ENLIGHT partner university and the surrounding societal ecosystem.

Assessment of DI/AI readiness and maturity

The table below is reflecting results obtained in Q1 2023 and focused on DI/AI readiness and maturity related to organizations and digital ecosystems. It can be considered as a baseline for future planning related to DI/AI within the ENLIGHT Alliance. There are at least three areas of uncertainty to be aware of when reading - all related the fact that only information available at the moment of collection can be reflected in the report:

- The DI/AI field is rapidly developing and the table reflects a somewhat retrospective view available at the moment of data collection.
- Availability of information in English may influence the results. There can very well be highly committed local hubs serving local users/business sector using another language than English.

- DI/AI is influencing the way we do research and innovation. New combinations of disciplines, not previously known for the use of digital/AI/experimental means, are created as a result.

Assessment of activity levels were made in five areas using information from different sources (e.g. search of web and databases, ChatGPT, previous work within ENLIGHT-RISE, and the partner contact points for WP 3). Results were summarized as an estimation of the activity level (1 = Low, 2 = Medium, 3 = High based on indicative guidance on what constitutes a high level of activity (e.g. mentioned at policy level, support service provided). Results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Assessment of DI/AI readiness and maturity in ENLIGHT partner universities.

DI/AI Track record (quantitative)										Input via websearch, ChatGPT (until Dec 2021) and ENLIGHT-RISE reports
Policy engagement										Membership in e.g. The Guild or other university networks with policy focus, EOSC, chairmanship etc.
SP3 (Strategy for Smart Specialization)										Country/region in SP3, involvement in thematic area of "Digital Innovation for Industry" via EDIH/DIH.
Institutional strategies										DRI and/or DI/AI as integrated part of an institutional strategy. Policies/plans for e.g. core facilities or OS.
Connectivity and coordination										Are local research strength coordinated with strategic support, policy instruments etc.
	CU	GAL	RUG	UBx	UGENT	UGOE	UPV/EHU	UT	UU	

The visualization above indicates both areas where information can be described by quantitative means (e.g. hits via search in database/web or involvement in policy groups) as well as areas where a YES or NO gives binary information (e.g. the presence of strategies). Most of these areas are targeted by all partners, while the activity levels and coverage over different disciplinary fields may vary substantially.

Synergies in the Digital Landscape to Identify ENLIGHT Priorities and Opportunities

In order to identify ENLIGHT assets, opportunities and priorities, information was obtained from different sources:

Connections between Universities and Flagship Challenges

The ENLIGHT-RISE application gave basic information about interaction and involvement in the five original Flagship Areas. Interconnections, as demonstrated by involvement in H2020-projects, are illustrated as a map over existing collaborations per flagship area and partner university.

Based on number of participating universities and critical mass of interactions give a semi-quantitative “ranking” strength and involvement per Flagship Area:

Flagship Area	Assessment of Critical Mass
Health and Well Being	
Digital Revolution & Impact of Digitalisation	
Energy and Circular Economy	
Climate Change	
Equity	

An effort was also made to find existing collaborative project in the field of AI. The undertaking was made via the Ubx European Project Office. The search for collaborative project via European funding or publications did not result in any identified active collaborations.

It may thus be concluded that the field of AI is attracting a lot of interest from many researchers as well as their institutions, but active collaborations within ENLIGHT are either to new to be found in databases or not yet existing.

[The use of DI/AI by ENLIGHT universities](#)

All ENLIGHT universities demonstrate activities in the area of DI/AI. Short presentations covering the involvement in DI/AI per university are presented in an Appendix.

Basic elements as departments performing research and education related to information technology, informatics, AI etc. are available in all ENLIGHT universities. Some observations:

- the ENLIGHT partners are all comprehensive research universities which is reflected in how is DI/AI appearing,
- many examples are demonstrating excellence in obvious areas as computer science or ICT,
- there are also many activities related to SSH including cross-over collaboration with STEM.
- collaborations involving the healthcare sector are frequent. These collaborations are sometimes focussing on rather disciplinary questions as e.g. the interface between genomics and personal medicine but there are also many initiatives aiming at empowering patients and develop solutions to promote e.g. healthy ageing or an active life for people with chronical disease.

However, the ways responsibilities as governance, ownership and funding are organized may differ. This is not so much based on strategic decisions by universities as on differences between national systems – see below.

- In some countries digital research infrastructure as e.g. data centres and digital innovation hubs are owned/hosted outside universities. It may be the case in e.g. Belgium or Germany. In others, as e.g. Sweden, the universities are the owners but funding may come from a national funding agency.
- The same situation goes for support functions as e.g. incubators, co-working spaces and possibilities to get legal advice. The ecosystems are comprising some common roles but operations may be funded and organized in many different ways.
- Sometimes strategic competence centres are organized outside universities, and in collaboration with societal partners. The university may be a partner on the same level as companies/ other stakeholders and have access to jointly funded resources. In some countries there is a powerful sector of research institutes. They are often very active on policy levels and in collaboration with universities (e.g. Germany/Max Planck, Helmholtz, Fraunhofer etc.). Estonia has a strong national commitment in research with strategies involving universities. Others are acting on a more regional basis, with the Basque Center for Applied Mathematics as an example of a centre of excellence operated outside the university but with strong university relations.

Acceleration of DI/AI transmission,

Actions to further strengthen the ENLIGHT Alliance

The ENLIGHT Alliance was initially formed by nine European universities around five Flagship Areas related to societal challenges. ENLIGHT has now been in operation for some years and set a transformative process in motion to achieve systemic change. In order to prepare for the future and strengthen the platform, decisions were taken to add a few strategic assets:

[The University of Bern \(CH\)](#) – Upon the application of a new funding period for ENLIGHT, a new associated HEI partner is introduced: the University of Bern. All ENLIGHT universities closely cooperate with the University of Bern across disciplines. Several ENLIGHT members are united with Bern via The Guild of European Research-Intensive Universities, an association of 21 renowned research-intensive European universities in 16 countries. Although Bern can only obtain the status of associated partner in the framework of the Erasmus+ project, Bern is committed to create capacity for ENLIGHT and contribute staff and funding resources to progressively participate in all ENLIGHT activities.

Culture and Creativity as a new ENLIGHT Flagship Area – Culture and Creativity is introduced as a new Flagship Area in order to safeguard culturally informed sustainable development that fosters cultural diversity, heritage, social cohesion, and cross-cultural understanding (SDG 4.7), with a special focus on: (i) History – understanding of Anthropocene/EU; (ii) Multilingualism; (iii) Art and music, education, innovation; (iv) Tourism and culture economy (local, EU). With these topics, ENLIGHT will connect with the EIT Culture and Creativity platform (launched in June 2022) of which two of our ENLIGHT partners, University of Tartu and Uppsala University, are founding members.

The above mentioned strategic steps are both of relevance to the positioning of the ENLIGHT Alliance and may contribute in policy issues as well as provide new opportunities for co-development between STEM and SHS in creative areas as arttech, augmented reality and gaming.

Strategy for Smart Specialization and Digital Innovation Hubs – a vast network of support

As part of the European Strategy for Smart Specialization (S3) the platform provides a combination of mapping tools that allow users to identify regional economic domains of specialization and aim at facilitating interregional cooperation and the creation of partnerships among various actors throughout Europe. As described in Table 1 the ENLIGHT universities are all working close to the European Strategy for Smart Specialization. However, the S3 is not primarily targeting universities and is more of an instrument for developing the regional business sector in order to boost economic growth.

The Network of European Digital Innovation Hubs (EDIH) is a pan-European initiative that aims to accelerate digital transformation throughout the European Union. The Digital Transformation Accelerator (DTA), with an objective to foster networking, cooperation and knowledge transfer activities between EDIH, SME and mid-caps, the public sector and other relevant stakeholders and initiatives, is managing the web presence of the network, hosting appropriate software platform and tools and including an up-to-date online catalogue of EDIHs. The online services and relevant/updated information are available via:

<https://european-digital-innovation-hubs.ec.europa.eu/home>

Presence of advanced industry clusters

In order to identify opportunities in the DI/AI Ecosystem not only research excellence and student opportunities are of importance – there must also be a business sector to interact with. Clusters related to the business sector can be understood as assets to further explore. However, the presence of a cluster in a certain area of competence

may reflect very different capacities related to strategies, impact, shared relationships, trust and funding schemes. The assessment presented in Table 2 is provided by ENLIGHT-RISE WP 5 in D 5.1-report.

Table 2: Advanced industry clusters

Advanced Industry Clusters	Auto-motive Environment ICT Tech	Creative Food ICT Life science Marine	Bio Circular Digital Health Smart	Agro AI Robotics Aeror Health Materials Photonic Social	Agro Biotech Pharma Photonic	Health Digital Logistics Tech	Aero Electro Energy Machine & Tooling Telecom	Biotech Defense Electro ICT Health Tech	Life Science Materials ICT	
Assessed by ENLIGHT WP 5	2	3	3-4	4	3	4	5	2	5	Degree of critical mass and maturity
	CU	GAL	RUG	UBx	UGENT	UGOE	UPV/EHU	UT	UU	

Legal challenges

A special set of challenges are differences in legislation between countries. Areas where differences are noteworthy are e.g.:

Management of IP

In many countries, IP created in research projects are considered to be property of the university. Universities are then managing portfolios of IP and do business in e.g. tech transfer or licensing to industry. In other countries, IP is a property of the researcher and not of the university.

In e.g. France and Sweden, researchers own IP as an individual (physical person). The researcher may also use a company in order to arrange an institutional ownership of IP (it is compulsory with some funding relationships). Most researcher are seldom-users in the IP area and do not run companies for their IP. *For such cases UU has a tool – RIPAB (Research Intellectual Property AB):* a holding company managing IP on behalf of researchers. RIPAB then act as an institutional owner of IP but any financial outcome is the property of the researcher and not of RIPAB or Uppsala university. Expertise in the area of contract and ownership of IP is an area of Legal Affairs and within the ENLIGHT Alliance there is a legal network with local representatives from all partners universities.

Public access to information and and confidentiality

Sweden is special here, as well. Uppsala university is a public authority and thus ruled by the "Principle of public access to information and secrecy" to make information publicly available. In many countries data is supposed to be open but not until after publication or other periods of embargo. On the other hand there are sometimes recommendations to avoid cloud based storage. For companies the possibilities to keep information confidential are the same in Sweden as in most countries. The EOSC is elaborating with a concept to keep information as open as possible but as closed as necessary. Reasons for keeping information confidential may be commercial or related to personal integrity.

This area of expertise is also related to the area of cybersecurity where information related to legislation can be obtained via legal support functions but advice about storage of data etc. may be provided through a data office or similar. How to manage, store and share data is an area to address when outlining the data management plan/DMP for a project. DMPOnline is a useful tool to create, review and manage plans that meet institutional and funder requirements.

R & I co-development of DI/AI between STEM and SSH

The digital interface between STEM and SHS is demonstrating interesting aspects of interaction between society, individuals and technology. In the Appendices a number of examples demonstrating a track record in digital innovation including multidisciplinary platforms or Centres of Excellence with STEM and SSH. Such examples are found in all ENLIGHT universities demonstrating not only a readiness but also experience in bringing together multidisciplinary teams with a positive and innovative result.

The digital world has for a long time been expected to change the way we do research and innovation. This is indeed true when completely new fields e.g. digital humanities, the gaming industry or possibilities to create immersive experiences by physio-digital means are developing. New business models, e.g. based on block-chain technology like NFT, are also giving openings for copyright on digital products.

Map over DI/AI Resources in the ENLIGHT Digital Ecosystem – alignment and coordination

Areas of competence in local DI/AI Ecosystems were identified on the basis of vertical alignment/coordination demonstrated by a presence of:

- 1) Research/education and Centers of excellence,
- 2) Support for DI/AI and data management,
- 3) Capacities in innovation support, as e.g. funding and legal advice/IP,
- 4) Innovation hubs/test beds and industry clusters,
- 5) Visibility via institutional strategies and platforms for stakeholders or policy makers.

In order to make societal impact, a great number of initiatives/projects in a variety of disciplinary fields are required but not sufficient. The presence of a value chain connected to the R&I Ecosystem is also of substantial importance in order to make impact. Such a value chain calls for bottom-up excellence but also a structure where the business sector, public stakeholders, decision makers, funding agencies etc. can

meet and interact. In the value chain there is also a need for facilities that can be used and leveraged for modelling, testing and validating new concepts. The map above illustrates how areas of competence related to ENLIGHT Flagships are distributed among DI/AI Ecosystems. For each partner university a selection of five areas of competence/partner fulfilling the demands of alignment were identified. These can be expected to be important in order to make impact in the area of DI/AI.

SUMMARY and RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the mapping exercises within ENLIGHT-RISE (mainly WP 3,5, and 7) demonstrates a rather well equipped landscape of DI/AI tools and services. Most of the partner universities within the Alliance are also committed to DI/AI via institutional strategies, membership in policy oriented organizations and involved in national efforts to foster a Green and Digital Europe.

Since the ENLIGHT Alliance is well positioned to take part in ongoing European work in the DI/AI area, a platform for future work may be based on guiding principles aligning with existing structures within and outside ENLIGHT as described below:

- 1) **Workflows within ENLIGHT** – Based on a federated model suggested earlier in D 3.1. the partner universities are responsible for their own internal processes, staffing and funding of *in house*-work. Output is then coordinated over the alliance by mechanisms approved by decision making bodies. How these are organized may vary between partners - however, the alliance partners are responsible for the capacity to provide information about local digital resources and competencies.
- 2) **Coordination and Alignment** – The diversity over organizations, innovation districts, and national “modus operandi” are a challenge. Even though there are tools and services in almost every disciplinary field – in academy as well as in industry – they may very well be of very different status. There are established, world leading centres with a broad scope but also small and new – private as well as public etc. And the field is rapidly developing! There are also sometimes very powerful centres of excellence in research departments but they are not part of a landscape with priorities to “service”.
- 3) **Information Management** – Another challenge is that information about resources, tools and services may be scattered and not available on central level in universities or not available in English. The mapping activities within ENLIGHT-RISE is one important step to keep track on assets. Focus is then on tools and services of critical mass and sustainability as presented in a map to further explore. Such centres are hubs for development and contact with the forefront in their area. They are also often aware of their local landscape including business sector and culture.

- 4) **Flagship Priorities** – It is an important observation that strategic priorities related to Flagship Challenges in a university coincide with infrastructural resources, tools and services, industrial clusters and access to incubators, education etc. The presence of such assets also reflects a track record in innovation. When ENLIGHT Thematic networks of researchers are formed and their priorities are defined it will be possible to get access to tools/services as e.g. HPC of different size and set-up, support for development and testing or cybersecurity. No obvious gaps are identified even though local capacities may vary. Within E-RISE WP 5 the Flagship “Health and Wellbeing” was identified as an area to start with. The present report supports the recommendation of WP 5 but will also add a recommendation around the Flagship “Digital Revolution & Impact of Digitalisation” where industrial interests are reflected by many local digital innovation hubs active in e.g. advanced manufacturing, robotics, ICT and creative industries. The “Digital” Flagship is also suitable for transdisciplinary work covering more than one ENLIGHT Flagship Area.
- 5) **From Theory to Practise** – Dialogues with university representatives within ENLIGHT-RISE WP 3 calls for access to hands-on support or e.g. protocols for guidance. These are not easy to find (or yet not existing). If there is a field to identify as a gap – this is it! The conclusion is also supported by e.g. dialogues related to EOSC where the Task Forces are currently busy with issues as “Semantic Interoperability” or “Technical Interoperability of Data and Services”. Within ENLIGHT-RISE D 3.2, three *case studies* are performed in order to gain further insights into how connecting and sharing of data can be achieved in practise. In certain areas achievements are made and lessons from them are brought into the ENLIGHT community. Digital Humanities/DARIAH and the European Covid-19 data portal (ELIXIR, now expanding to surveillance of other pathogens/pandemics) are important examples.

As stated in D 3.1-report it still must be stressed that differences in legislation and administrative/business traditions between countries are – and will be so for a long time – an ongoing struggle to overcome. EUN/ENLIGHT is a tool and an effort to take on the challenge but not a final solution to hand over a R/I-community where all obstacles are removed after a first three-year period. There will also be an obvious need for upskilling. Such upskilling may be provided within e.g. ENLIGHT during the upcoming funding period (WP 3 and WP 4) and with focus on academic needs but it can also be accessible via EOSC, digital innovation hubs or larger research infrastructures organizing upskilling for users in their target disciplinary user communities.

APPENDICES

The DI/AI Ecosystem around each ENLIGHT partner university is described in an appendix (two pages per partner).

The digital world is very much about sharing and connecting – and it is rapidly developing. It is also an area where geography and physical borders are less important. When looking at the digital ecosystems it is obvious that there is a strong commitment from universities, regions, states and the EC. The private sector is also very active with a variety of companies – small/local as well as huge/global – and research institutes etc.

When describing the ecosystems there are similarities and repeated roles (e.g. department as well as support functions as a digital research infrastructure, data centre or digital innovation hub) but how they are organized and funded may differ between countries. ENLIGHT universities are e.g. often partners in national platforms but these can be situated elsewhere since geography is of less importance.

The appendices give short information about the DI/AI Ecosystem and provide weblinks to organizational functions (including updated information). In general support functions as data centres and innovation hubs are well equipped to give advice within their field of expertise and have excellent professional networks. They are also very often providers of state-of-the-art tools and services including data stewards to help onboarding users.

University of Bordeaux (UBx)

The university has a Department of Engineering and digital sciences with four research centers focus on various aspects of digital innovation. It leads a research network on robotics and autonomous systems (RobSys). Major national research chairs for AI and a priority research programs (PEPR) for AI are:

- GrAI Green (Green AI)
- Intended (Reasoning for improved access to imperfect data)
- Deep Curiosity (Child cognitive development approach applied to AI)
- PEPR Artificial Intelligence

The department is also involved in five research task forces:

- RobSys (robustness of autonomous systems)
- BRAIN_2030 (Future of neurosciences in Nouvelle-Aquitaine region)
- BEST (Making better to live better)
- LIGHT (Light sciences and its applications)
- PPM (Post-Petroleum Materials)

UBx also partners the private sector to help drive digital innovation, and it offers a range of education and training programs to students and professionals to help them develop the skills they need to succeed in the digital economy.

Examples on outcomes are e.g.

- Smart City Technologies with a number of technologies, including systems for monitoring air/water quality, traffic management, and energy management. A data-driven, smart building for high level sports training is under development.
- In the area of Biomedical and Health Technologies including systems for monitoring vital signs, disease diagnosis, and patient monitoring has been developed with a strong support of our TTO to accelerate start-up creation (e.g. TreeFrog Therapeutics, ReBrain, MyMedA ...).
- In Virtual Reality and Augmented Reality there is a positive track record, including systems for telepresence, gaming, and education.

UBx holds a "trustworthy AI" patronage chair and a doctoral program for transdisciplinary AI. The University of Bordeaux is laureate of a national program for AI training and its AI training program will launch in September 2023.

There are several **support functions for digital innovation** including:

1. Incubators/accelerators provide support to startups and entrepreneurs in the digital sector; e.g. technology parks and innovation centres such as our pre-maturation program, the Spark program, our TTO (AST) and its incubator (Chrysalink), our students incubator (UBeeLab), the Inria's incubator (Inria Startup Studio), offer a range of services, including mentoring, networking, and access to funding
2. Support to businesses and organizations including research and development, prototyping, and testing. Bordeaux has a number of investment funds investing in a wide range of digital innovations, including software, hardware, and services.
3. Professional networks that bring together entrepreneurs, researchers, and business leaders in the digital sector sharing
4. The region of Nouvelle-Aquitaine have a dedicated Digital Agency and a Regional Council which offers a range of supports and funding for digital innovation projects.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

Campus@DATACENTER aims at building shared cloud services on top of the forthcoming regional (New Aquitaine) cloud datacenter

DOREMI aims at building shared computing infrastructures for research institutions at the regional level.

Additionally, UBx also has a range of partnerships with private companies, such as Airbus, CapGemini, Siemens and Google Zurich, which provide access to additional resources and support for digital research and innovation.

Is there competence related to sensitive data in UBx?

The university of Bordeaux has a data protection officer (DPO) for all GDPR-related questions; an agent dedicated to the risk analysis of, and legal expertise on, sensitive data in research programs.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

DIHNAMIC (Aquitaine Manufacturing Industry Community) – active in four major areas: AI as a service, intelligent systems and infrastructures, robotics/agile processes/human-systems interfaces and mock-ups and digital twins (optimizations).

Tools, Best practice?

UBx is fully committed to the acceleration of research in data science and artificial intelligence as supported by the national French strategy and offer a research program and education from undergraduate to doctorate.

University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU)

Dept. of Computer Science and AI – strengths in machine learning, visualization, language processing and robotics. Faculty of Informatics: <https://www.ehu.eus/en/web/informatika-fakultatea/ikerketa-lerroak>

Aeronautics Advanced Manufacturing Center (CAFA):
<https://www.ehu.eus/en/web/cafa/home>

Basque Center for Applied Mathematics (BCAM) <http://www.bcamath.org/en/the-center/presentation>

Basque Cybersecurity Center (BCSC). <https://www.basquecybersecuritycentre.com/>

Research centers partnered with industry:

Basque Artificial Intelligence Center (BAIC) <https://www.baic.eus/en/>

There are several **support functions for digital innovation** in the Basque Country where initiatives and programs support digital innovation and technology-based startups. In summary, the Basque Country has a supportive ecosystem for digital innovation, with a range of initiatives, programs, and resources available to support entrepreneurs, startups, and technology-based companies.

1. The Basque Government's Department of Economic Development, Sustainability and Environment has an Innovation Unit that aims to promote innovation and entrepreneurship in the region. It provides funding and support for startups and technology-based companies through various programs and initiatives.

<https://www.spri.eus/en/>

2. The Basque Country has a number of technology parks and innovation centers such as TECNALIA, the Basque Country's leading private applied research center, and IK4-TEKNIKER, which is an applied research center that focuses on advanced manufacturing and industrial technologies. <https://www.tecnalia.com/en/> and

https://www.tekniker.es/es/research_alliance

3. The Basque Centre for Innovation is a non-profit organization that aims to promote innovation and entrepreneurship in the Basque Country. It provides a range of services such as networking events, mentoring, and access to funding and other resources to help entrepreneurs and startups succeed.

4. The Basque Government also offers a range of tax incentives, subsidies and other support to companies that invest in innovation and R&D activities. There are also a number of venture capital firms and angel investors that provide funding and support to startups and technology-based companies.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

Yes, the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) has a range of digital research infrastructure that supports digital innovation and artificial intelligence (AI) research:

High-performance computing (HPC) resources: The UPV/EHU has access to a number of high-performance computing resources, such as HPC-ARINA at Advanced Research Facilities (SGIKer)-UPV/EHU, HPC-ATLAS at Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC) and the Mare Nostrum supercomputer (one of the most powerful supercomputers in Europe): <https://www.ehu.es/en/web/sgiker/ikerketari-aplikatutako-informatika-kalkulu-zientifikoa-tresnak>, <https://cc.dipc.org/>

Hitz Basque Center for Language Technology (Hitz-UPV/EHU), CLARIAH-ES y CLARIAH-EU. CLARIN has also recognized Spanish CLARIN Knowledge Centre; <https://www.hitz.eus/>

Research labs and facilities: The UPV/EHU has a number of research labs and facilities that support digital innovation and AI research, such as the Robotics and Perception Group, which focuses on computer vision, robotics, and machine learning, and the Natural Language Processing Group.

Is there competence related to sensitive data in UPV/EHU?

UPV/EHU has expertise within a range of research groups, centers, programs, and collaborations related to sensitive data, including data privacy and security, e.g..

1. Several research groups and centers focus on data privacy and security, such as the Security and Trust in Computing Systems (STCS) research group, which focuses on the design and evaluation of secure systems and protocols, and the Center for Cybersecurity and Privacy (CSP),
2. UPV/EHU also offers education in data privacy and security, such as a Master's degree in Cybersecurity and a M.Sc. in Computer Engineering (data privacy and security).
3. The university has also conducted research on data privacy and security in various application domains, such as Internet of Things (IoT) security, blockchain security, and secure communication protocols for smart grids.
4. UPV/EHU has also implemented a data protection policy in order to ensure the confidentiality, integrity and availability of data, as well as to prevent data breaches and unauthorized access to sensitive information.

Digital Innovation Hubs in Ecosystem?

Basque Digital Innovation Hub - The Basque Digital Innovation Hub - BDIH in Health has the infrastructure provided by all the RTOs (Research & Transfer Organizations), universities, companies, and the Basque healthcare system.

Comenius University (CU)

Two departments in Computer Science and Applied Informatics, department of Didactics with activities related to Informatics at Faculty of mathematics, physics, and informatics. Department of Library and Information Science (Faculty of Arts).

Computational Biology Research group : <http://compbio.fmph.uniba.sk/>

Cognition and Neural Computation group <https://cogsci.fmph.uniba.sk/cnc/>

In the area of data science and health psychology, mobile app helps people recover from substance abuse,

In the area of Science, Technology and Humanity: Opportunities and Risks Artificial minds, artificial persons attract interest and raise important ethical questions. There are also projects related to Smart Cities.

Comenius University also partners with companies and organizations in the private sector to help drive digital innovation Slovak AI - National platform for the AI development in Slovakia, company ESET, R-DAS and others.

No specific support unit available for digital innovation.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

No dedicated research infrastructures – however, Faculty of mathematics, physics, and informatics as primary place, where research on digital innovation and AI is conducted, can be regarded as such one.

Is there competence related to sensitive data in CU?

Standard Data Protection Office is established at central administrative level.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

Several DIH:s are active in the Bratislava Ecosystem including:

SAS Institute of Informatics (Slovak Acad, of Sciences) including HPC, AI, IoT

National Centre of Robotics, Bratislava

EDIH Bratislava with support for Additive manufacturing, AI, Big Data, Imaging and Gaming

SKAI-EDIH – centre for innovative healthcare with focus on AI.

Tools, Best practice?

PANGAIA: Developing Computational Pangenomics:

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/872539>

Other: <https://fmph.uniba.sk/en/research/selected-research-projects/>

New projects focused on training experts and building new capacities:

TERAIS: Towards Excellent Robotics and Artificial Intelligence at a Slovak university,

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101079338>

TRAIL: TRANSPARENT INTERPRETABLE robots / Training robotics experts,

<https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101072488>

University of Galway (Gal)

University of Galway has a strong strategic focus where digital competencies and capacities within data and enabling technologies present in many fields data science, business information systems, artificial intelligence, advanced computing platforms and services, laser and optics. The University of Galway also has research centers with focus on various aspects of the digital world:

The Data Science Institute (DSI), research technologies at the convergence of Computer Science, Web Science and Artificial Intelligence to build a fundamental understanding of how information and knowledge are increasingly driving society through digital processes, and of the tools, techniques and principles supporting a data-enhanced world.

The Moore Institute Digital Lab provides researchers in the Arts, Humanities and Social Studies with access to digital technologies, skills and people to help develop the digital dimension of their work.

The Social Science Computing Hub is in the Whitaker Institute offer e-infrastructure for business and social sciences analytics offering a wide range of cross disciplinary workshops to generate a multidisciplinary perspective in addressing global and regional Public Policy issues.

The University of Galway also partners with the private sector to help drive digital innovation, and it offers a range of education and training programs developing the skills they need to succeed in the digital economy. As an institution of enterprise, research and learning, University of Galway fosters strategic global engagement through partnerships, research networks, and other collaborative activities between the University and partners globally.

There are several **support functions for digital innovation** including:

1. The Innovation Office catalyses and accelerates the impact of research and innovation. Acceleration is obtained by engaging with external stakeholders, working closely with our research community, and supporting new ventures.
2. Galway University's Business Innovation Centre is at the heart of our university's innovation ecosystem. BIC provide extensive laboratories, dedicated offices, co-working spaces and research infrastructure. Through a programme of supports designed for ambitious start-ups, the Innovation Office team offer mentoring, business development guidance, commercial and IP guidance - as well as access to research expertise.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

University of Galway is home to the Irish Centre for High-End Computing (ICHEC) which was established in 2005 and accommodated as part of University of Galway's College of

Science and Engineering. ICHEC's operations encompass big data, data analytics, data handling, machine learning, federated learning, and artificial intelligence. Insight

University of Galway is one of four lead Irish HEIs in Insight, the Science foundation Ireland (SFI) Insight Centre for Data Analytics. Insight is involved in projects including HPC/BigData, Cyber physical systems, IoT, AI, Cyber security, New media

Is there competence related to sensitive data in Gal?

University of Galway has a Research Protection Office and Officer. In the context of data management planning and practice, the James Hardiman Library on the University of Galway campus also has competency in handling and sharing sensitive data.

<https://libguides>. In addition, the Hardiman offers guidance on GDPR compliance and assessment tools including a Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) checklist.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

The DSI is part of University of Galway's greater Computer Science research and development core. The research undertaken at DSI includes data technologies at the convergence of Computer Science, Web Science and Artificial Intelligence to understand how information is driving society. DSI is actively engaged in a variety of collaborative National and International projects.

The Insight Centre supports work in the Fundamentals of Data Science, Sensing and Actuation, Scaling Algorithms, Model Building, Multi Modal Analysis, Data Engineering and Governance, Decision Making and Trustworthy AI.

Through Insight, University of Galway as lead (current):

NURS-ULG, Stair4Security CEN, Multi-Level Smart City Sustainable EcoSystems

ICHEC is a National Centre for High-Performance Computing (HPC) providing e-infrastructure, services and expertise to academia, industry and the public sector supported by the Department of Further and Higher Education, Research, Innovation and Skills and the Higher Education Authority.

Tools, Best practice?

The University of Galway is fully committed to the acceleration of research in data science and artificial intelligence. Many projects are illustrating best practice including partnership with industry. These include the SFI Insight Center itself and its associated projects, CRFG clinical, ICHEC's partnerships with Intel, DDN, ExSeisDat, Skytek, Tullow Oil, Xilinx, ICHEC's collaborations with H2020 funded projects through collaboration in E-CAM, ESCAPE, ESIWACE, HPC Europa 3, PRACE, READEX, SESAME Net and others. The SFI-funded UniCOV mass Covid-19 testing project, AIRSTREAM and the associated climate modeling are also examples.

Ghent University (UGent)

Ghent University has research and education in different areas where digital skills are important, e.g. a Master of Science Program Bioinformatics which is embedded in a strong bioinformatics and biotechnology research environment and affiliated with VIB and IMEC.

Furthermore, more and more attention is going specifically to the field of Artificial Intelligence (AI). The following UGent Faculties are currently active in AI: Engineering and Architecture, Bio-Science Engineering, Sciences, Economics and Business Administration, Arts and Philosophy, Psychology and Educational Sciences, Medicine and Health Sciences, Law and Criminology, Political and Social Sciences. AI is also explicitly part of the UGent educational program.

The Ghent Center for Digital Humanities is an interdisciplinary research and service centre that facilitates and reflects on the use of digital research methods in the humanities. A team of computer scientists, linguists, data scientists, interdisciplinary 'digital humanists' and public historians is clustered in four focus areas: collaborative databases and Linked Open Data - digitization, (pre)processing and digital text and image analysis - geospatial analysis and visualization - digital heritage, participation and virtual exhibitions.

Dwengo is developing innovative workshops and educational resources - and provide them to students around the globe. Focus areas are e.g. how AI help to give insights into climate and nature and the use of social robots.

DELTA - Digital innovation for man and society - wants to put digital innovation back at the service of people and society. That is why Delta is bringing researchers together with policymakers, entrepreneurs and civil society organizations to explore the possibilities of the very latest technologies and steers digital innovation in the desired direction.

The Ghent University also partners with companies and organizations in the private sector to help drive digital innovation, and it offers a range of education and training programs to students and professionals to help them develop skills for the digital economy.

There are also **support functions for digital innovation** including:

The Department of Economy, Science, and innovation (ESI) is involved in the AI Barometer, This AI Barometer maps the adoption, use and competence in Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Flemish businesses. Almost one-quarter (23.3 percent) of Flemish businesses use at least one AI technology in their business operations.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

- VSC – Ghent University is partner in the Flemish Supercomputer Center (VSC – <https://www.vscentrum.be>) which aims at the national Flemish level to encourage the use of scientific and technical computing in the academic and industrial landscape.
- EuroCC NCC – Ghent University is partner in the Belgian EuroCC National Competence Center (<https://www.enccb.be>). This center aims at the Belgian national level to coordinate activities in the area of HPC, artificial intelligence and high-performance data analytics, and to serve as a contact point for customers from industry, science, (future) HPC experts, and the general public alike.
- DMPOnline – Ghent University manages the Belgian DMPOnline infrastructure for managing Data Management Plans (<https://dmponline.be>).

Is there competence related to sensitive data in UGENT?

Yes. Competence can be found in e.g. the bioinformatics area related to ELIXIR but also via support for data management. The Research Data Management Team has a course for early career researchers where data protection and sensitive data is a part.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

- EDIH4Agrifood – HPC, AI, BigData, Cybersecurity, IoT
- Flanders AI EDIH – incubator, market intelligence, testing/validating, brokerage

Tools, Best practice?

- ELIXIR-BELGIUM (<https://www.elixir-belgium.org>) - The distributed infrastructure for life science information consolidates national centres, services, and core bioinformatic resources into a single, coordinated infrastructure. ELIXIR coordinates and develops life science resources across Europe, enabling researchers to find, analyze and share data, exchange expertise and implement best practices.
- EMBRC- European Marine Biological Resource Centre (<https://www.embrc.be>)

EMBRC-ERIC is a European Research Infrastructure Cluster that provides and supports large-scale, high-quality marine biological and ecological research in Europe. It was established to address Europe's challenges related to food, health and global change.

- FIRE (Fostering Innovative Research based on Evidence)
Young academics need access to expert advice in statistics and methodology in order to maintain scientific integrity and publish reproducible research. FIRE support PhD students and postdocs and give advice may related including study design, data collection, statistical analysis, and the interpretation and reporting of study results to early career researchers.

University of Groningen (UG)

The University of Groningen is fully committed to DI/AI and the home of a broad range of initiatives, e.g. education in AI with programs on Bachelor and Master levels. Strategic priorities of UG are sustainability, energy, health, agricultural transition and circular economy – all of them include aspects of DI/AI. Examples below:

Data Science and Systems Complexity (<https://www.rug.nl/research/fse/themes/dssc/>) is a research cluster of 58+ senior researchers working in a number of basic disciplines. The ambition is to combine data science and complexity science to solve the challenges arising when complex systems and big data collide.

Smart Industries: (<https://www.rug.nl/research/researchthemes/smart-industries>) brings together fundamental and engineering sciences. Activities are organized in areas as Business Innovation, Advanced Production Processes, Agile demand-driven manufacturing and Embedded intelligence.

The interface between STEM and SHS is explored in e.g. interaction between humans and new technologies, with specific attention to language-based technologies. Innovation is geared towards human-human and human-machine interaction and “Democracy and Digitalization”.

There are also **support functions for digital innovation** including University of Groningen Centre of Entrepreneurship based on three pillars: engaged education, excellent research and active business development support. There is also a “Digital Society Hub” - a living lab where students, lecturers, researchers and entrepreneurs work together on the latest technological developments. The Digital Society Hub is an inspiring workplace where multidisciplinary teams will develop new products and applications relating to 5G, big data and e-health. The hub develops applications using e.g. VR, AR, games and drones.

There is also an Innovation Center (UG and the University Medical Centre) in healthcare and starting point for developing and implementing healthcare innovations including in the digital area. The UG is involved in public-private partnerships, most prominently in the sectors Health and Energy.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

The UG-Digital Competence Centre (DCC, www.rug.nl/dcc) support the entire research (data) life cycle, from grant proposal to FAIR data archiving. The UG infrastructure includes top-end HPC facilities (Hábrók), a Virtual Research Environment, managed research data storage facilities (RDMS based on iRODS), Data Science services, Astronomic databases (Astro Wise, EUCLID), Spatial Data Infrastructure and Elab journal.

At a national level the UG is connected to Surf IT for cooperation in support of education and research (www.surf.nl). UG is also connected to DTL hotel (I = life sciences); Health Research Infrastructure (health-ri.nl); NWO (Dutch Research Council) national scientific infrastructure;

Dutch AI Coalition (NL AIC) - LCRDM (landelijk coördinatiepunt voor research data management: <https://www.lcrdm.nl/en>); NWO Thematic Digital Competence Centers (<https://www.nwo.nl/en/news/setup-thematic-digital-competence-centers>); Mining Big Data field labs; dHealth (IT infrastructure for scientific research in healthcare); 5G fieldlabs (Internet of Things); B3Care (multi-party computation / federated learning); XNAT (analyzing (sensitive) medical data); ODISSEI (<https://odissei-data.nl/en/>); Clariah (<https://www.clariah.nl/>). Findability of UG research data and other research output is enhanced by the Research portal <https://research.rug.nl/en/datasets/>.

Is there competence related to sensitive data in RUG?

Yes, the DCC provides expertise on privacy and data protection in research. Together with the DPO and the Chief Privacy Officer and researchers a procedure for DPIA's in research projects was developed and implemented.

In collaboration with Statistics Netherlands and Maastricht University the UG develops expertise on privacy-preserving techniques. Researchers are working in e.g. bioinformatics/genomics, the social sciences and studies on language & cognition.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

The ICCS Innovation Centre deploys the latest (wireless) communication technology as sensor networks, IoT, BigData, and Tech. ICCS collaborates with other national 5G hubs, the AI hub, ASTRON and the Wireless Datalab, the TechHub, IT hub, Smart Industry Hub and the knowledge institutions in the Northern Netherlands at MBO, HBO and WO level.

The Digital Innovation Hub for the Northern Netherlands is active in the area of Smart Industries, HPC, AI, Cybersecurity, IoT, Manufacturing,

Tools, Best practice?

MOLGENIS is a free data platform for researchers to accelerate scientific collaborations and bioinformaticians. Molgenis, based on Open Source, helps to find, capture, exchange, manage and analyze scientific data. It is fully customizable: data structure, user interface and layout can be fully changed and you can plug-in your own (bioinformatics) scripts.

The UG is involved in activities on "Best Practise in Academic Integrity" with partners around Europe. One of the results is an innovative educational program on Privacy and Data Protection in Research: https://rm.coe.int/bpp_-a-compendium-of-best-practices-eng-/1680a86621

The interface between STEM and SHS is explored in e.g interaction between humans and new technologies, with specific attention to language-based technologies. Innovation is geared towards human-human and human-machine interaction and "Democracy and Digitalization". The Jantina Tammes School is the University of Groningen interdisciplinary center dedicated to digital society, technology and artificial intelligence

University of Göttingen (UGOE)

The University of Göttingen (UGOE) is active in research and education in various research areas where data science skills and infrastructures are important. The Faculty of Natural Sciences, Mathematics and Informatics offers attractive study programmes, e.g. Bachelor's programs in Mathematics and Applied Computer Science, Master's programs in Mathematics, Business Mathematics and Applied Computer Science, teacher training programs with the subject combination Mathematics and Computer Science and 17 other combinations with Mathematics or Computer Science.

A strong track record goes with research in about 20 areas of Computer Science, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/619486.html>, e.g. Neural Data Science, Scientific Information Analytics, Optimal Transport and Data Science Infrastructures.

Departments with major focus on Research and Education in DI/AI:

The Center for Computational Sciences <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/the+center/208376.html>, organizes, coordinates and performs research projects in the area of Computer Science and its applications.

Faculty of Business and Economics, e.g. Digital Health, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/632922.html>; Smart Mobility, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/smart+mobility/450340.html>

University Medical Center Göttingen (UMG), e.g. Epidemiology, Oncology

Centers of Excellence / research centers of relevance for DI/AI:

The [Cluster of Excellence Multiscale Bioimaging: from molecular machines to networks of excitable cells](#) (MBExC) aims to understand the connection between heart and brain diseases, to link basic and clinical research, and to develop new therapeutic and diagnostic approaches.

The [Göttingen Centre for Digital Humanities \(GCDH\)](#) doing research, teaching and development with the intersection of computational sciences and humanities.

The Bernstein Center for Computational Neuroscience Göttingen (BCCN), <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/615262.html>, is an interdisciplinary research center focusing on the exploration of the dynamics and adaptivity of the nervous system. It unites researchers in the fields of biology, physics, computer science, psychology, and medicine at the Göttingen Campus.

KISSKI, a highly available AI service centre for sensitive and critical infrastructures, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/669668.html>, aims to develop tailored AI-as-a-Service solutions to address the increasing demands in the field of artificial intelligence, especially concerning medical and energy-related infrastructures.

The [Campus Institute Data Science](#) (CIDAS) is a cross-campus structure to coordinate, implement and further develop research, teaching and training activities in the field of data science. Data Science competences are considered an essential core competence in all research areas of the Göttingen Campus. The teaching of data science in teaching, transfer and science communication plays a similarly central role.

[Göttingen Campus Institute for Dynamics of Biological Networks \(CIDBN\)](#) is a transdisciplinary institute at the Göttingen Campus, jointly sustained by the University, the University Medical Center, the [German Primate Center](#) and the [Max Planck Institute for Dynamics and Self-Organization](#).

Partnerships with organizations involving DI/AI:

Digital Health, e.g. CAEHR – Enhancing healthcare through intelligent data integration, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/648937.html>

Smart Mobility, e.g. KI_IDENT project, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/672441.html>

There are also **support functions for digital innovation** including the Knowledge and TechTransfer Office in collaboration with the University Medical Center Göttingen and MBM Science Bridge. MGM Science Bridge evaluate, protect and commercialize inventions from higher education institutions and research facilities. Support is given in areas as Medtech, Agrotech, Software and Life Sciences.

CIDAS/Sartorius QuCellAI Quantitative Cell Analytics Initiative: <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/de/666896.html>

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

The GWDG as a data and IT service is providing a broad range of services from HPC and cybersecurity to Data Analytics and courses.

UGOE is partner in several National Research Data Infrastructure consortia, e.g. NFDI4Biodiversity, NFDI4Chem, NFDI4Earth (<https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/3240.html?id=6007>, <https://www.uni-goettingen.de/en/3240.html?id=6320>), (<https://www.eresearch.uni-goettingen.de/news/gottingen-campus-news-nfdi-consortia-with-gottingen-participation-to-be-expanded-in-2023/>); CLARIAH-DE, <https://www.clariah.de/en/>

Is there competence related to sensitive data in UGOE?

Yes, in particular KISSKI mentioned above addresses sensitive data issues.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

IT Innovations Cluster Göttingen / Lower Saxony, <https://www.it-in-goe.de/>

Digital Innovation Days Lower Saxony, <https://digitaltag.eu/digitale-innovationen-in-suedniedersachsen>

University of Tartu (UT)

The University of Tartu is the only classical university in Estonia to do research in arts and humanities, social sciences, medical sciences and science and technology. Digital Humanities, Life Sciences/Bioinformatics and AI are strong research fields.

Activities in the DI/AI area are e.g.:

- The 3D printing technology of drugs is being developed at the Institute of Pharmacy of the University of Tartu. The purpose of that is to better prevent, diagnose and treat diseases.
- The R&D centre led by the University of Tartu will combine synthetic biology with digital technologies to facilitate big data-driven design of cells for the bio-industry, boosting both research and the development of new businesses based on industrial biotechnology.

There are also support functions for digital innovation including the Estonian Centre of Excellence in ICT Research - Developing Secure and Reliable IT Services and Systems. Excellent research by building synergies between Estonian research groups in IT. Cooperation projects between research groups from different IT research fields. Consolidating IT research community and increasing public awareness of IT research,

In Startup Day, the entrepreneurial researchers of the university meet mentors and investors who help them develop their research projects, e.g. into a deep-tech company.

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

The High Performance Computing Center is a consortium of UT and its purpose is to maintain and develop the infrastructure for scientific computing. The resources are open for use to any research groups from the university and other Estonian science- and research institutions are also welcome.

Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration (NeIC) - Estonia joined as a full member with ETAIS playing an important role in the process as well as coordination of projects from Estonian side.

The Estonian Education and Research Network EENet operates as a subunit of the Technology Management Department of the Ministry of Education and Research. The mission of EENet is to provide a high-quality national network infrastructure for Estonia's research, educational and cultural communities. Its services include permanent Internet connections, Eduroam, DNS, user support for several information systems of education etc.

SoBigData++ strives to deliver a distributed, Pan-European, multi-disciplinary research infrastructure for big social data analytics, coupled with the consolidation of a cross-disciplinary European research community, aimed at using social mining and big data to understand the complexity of our contemporary, globally-interconnected society. <https://plusplus.sobigdata.eu/>

Is there competence related to sensitive data in UT?

Yes, research related to e.g. Bioinformatics/genomics or within the social sciences are regularly working with sensitive data.

Digital Innovation Hubs?

AIRE, or AI & Robotics Estonia, is a technology hub dedicated to making Estonian manufacturing more competitive by helping businesses to introduce artificial intelligence and robotics solutions. AIRE helps drive innovation in industry by bringing together the ideas of universities and the needs of businesses in IT, engineering, robotics and electronics, to create a platform for businesses to develop digitalization and automation.

Tools, Best practice?

Some examples are:

- Hospital fear is a big problem in children who may be very afraid of some medical procedure. Holograms are one of the behavioral distraction techniques that are considered the most effective non-pharmacological techniques for reducing pain and fear.
- Cyberattacks threaten many computer-controlled systems. Attacks on technology, on which people's lives depend, are particularly dangerous. The functioning components of many terrestrial systems are located in space. One example of a cyberthreat is the manipulation of GPS satellites to block signals from them or cause them to transmit false signals. In cooperation with the University of Tartu Observatory and CybExer, is planning to create a digital twin from the ESTCube-2 satellite control system. On the twin, it is possible to test and develop the system's resistance to cyberattacks and to improve the original control system based on the experience gained. It can also be used to train satellite operators.
- The BalticSatApps project highlighted the possibilities of using free satellite data in the development of innovative services and products. Earth observation satellite data is available to everyone and anyone can get information on, for example, climate change or urban development.

Departments with major focus on Research and Education in DI/AI:

Department of Information Technology - Teaching and research focusing on advanced design and use of computer systems in science and technology:

<http://www.it.uu.se/first?lang=en>

Department of Informatics and Media (IM) develops knowledge on the current and future modes of communication and information distribution:

<https://www.im.uu.se/?languageld=1>

Department of Game Design are conducting research and educating in game design and related subjects, such as expression in convergent media, programming and project management: <https://www.speldesign.uu.se/?languageld=1>

Centres of Excellence/research centres of relevance to DI/AI:

AI4Research is a creative hub in order to coordinate and exploit the field of AI:

<https://www.uu.se/en/research/ai4research/>

Research centres in e-science: <https://www.it.uu.se/research/research-centres>

Uppsala Clinical Research Centre – a clinical Academic Research platform providing in-house expertise including management of clinical and observational studies, biostatistics, clinical quality registries, and clinical event adjudication: <https://www.ucr.uu.se/en/>

Centre for Digital Humanities: <https://www.abm.uu.se/cdhu-eng/>

Additive Manufacturing for the Life Sciences: <https://www.uu.se/en/research/am4life/>

SweDeliver - Research forum in drug delivery, focusing on new strategies for parenteral, oral and pulmonary drug delivery:

<https://www.uu.se/forskning/swedeliver/?languageld=1>

SOLVE - Solar Electricity Research Centre: <https://www.uu.se/forskning/solve/>

BASE/Batteries Sweden – and Alliance for Ultrahigh Performance Batteries:

<https://www.batteriessweden.se/>

Uppsala Peace and Conflict Data Program: <https://ucdp.uu.se/>

Partnerships with organizations involving DI/AI:

Strategic partnerships with potential in the DI/AI area:

<https://www.uu.se/en/collaboration/collaborations-partners/>

University Hospital: <https://www.uu.se/en/collaboration/university-hospital/>

There are also **support functions for digital innovation** including:

Support for researchers and students to identify, evaluate and develop innovative ideas: <https://www.uuinnovation.uu.se/?languageId=1>

Uppsala University Innovation Partnership Office – support for companies/organization seeking collaboration with researchers/students: <https://www.uu.se/en/collaboration/develop-with-uppsala-university/uppsala-university-innovation-partnership-office/>

Uppsala Innovation Centre (Business Incubator): <https://uic.se/>

Is there digital research infrastructure supporting digital innovation and AI?

UPPMAX (Uppsala Multidisciplinary Center for Advanced Computational Science) is Uppsala University's resource of high-performance computers, large-scale storage and know-how of high-performance computing (HPC): <https://www.uppmax.uu.se/>

SciLifeLab Data Centre – a major hub for activities throughout the life cycle of data in life sciences - from project planning, data production, data analysis, data sharing, to publishing and reuse of data, where researchers are dependent on advanced data analysis and e-infrastructures.: <https://www.scilifelab.se/data/>

The Swedish EuroCC Hub for High-Performance Computing - a national centre supporting industry, public administration and academia accessing and using European supercomputers: <https://enccs.se/>

Language Technology (CLARIN-ERIC): <https://www.uu.se/en/research/research-infrastructure/international-research-infrastructures-in-which-uppsala-university-participates/european-research-infrastructure-for-language-resources-and-technology-clarin-eric/>

Data portal for green-house gases (ICOS-ERIC): <https://www.uu.se/en/research/research-infrastructure/national-research-infrastructures-in-which-uppsala-university-participates/integrated-carbon-observation-system-icos-sweden/>

Is there competence related to sensitive data and cybersecurity in UU?

Yes, in data centres listed above and <http://www.it.uu.se/research/research-arenas/security?lang=en>

In the Legal Office there is a Data Protection Officer and a contact officer for legal affairs related to ENLIGHT: juravd@uadm.uu.se

Digital Innovation Hubs?

Swedish DIH are accessible via: <https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/tools>